
Research Article

Nomenclatural novelties in *Hoya* (Apocynaceae, Asclepiadoideae, Marsdenieae)

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Abstract: New names *Hoya panyupayanensis* Sanjeet Kumar & R.Kr. Singh and *H. robertii* Sanjeet Kumar & R.Kr. Singh are proposed here for *Eriostemma samarense* Kloppenb. and *E. davaoensis* Kloppenb., respectively.

Keywords: Endemic, *Eriostemma davaoense*, *Eriostemma samarense*, New name, Philippines

Introduction

The genus *Hoya* R.Br. comprises about 572 species, including five species formerly described under *Eriostemma* (Schltr.) Kloppenb. & Gilding, and is distributed throughout tropical & subtropical Asia to the western Pacific (POWO, 2025; Singh & Kumar, 2025). In the Philippines alone, about 197 species are recorded, of which 179 are endemic (POWO, 2025). Recent phylogenetic studies have incorporated *Eriostemma* (\equiv *Hoya* sect. *Eriostemma* Schltr.) within the genus *Hoya*, which belongs to the family Apocynaceae, subfamily Asclepiadoideae, and tribe Marsdenieae (Rodda et al., 2020; Liede-Schumann et al., 2022). Singh & Kumar (2025) proposed new combinations for *Eriostemma davaoense* Kloppenb. [*Hoya* New 2(3): 26. 2014] and *E. samarense* Kloppenb. [*Hoya* New 2(4): 4. 2014] under the genus *Hoya* as *H. davaoensis* (Kloppenb.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar and *H. samarensis* (Kloppenb.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, respectively. However, both names are illegitimate under Article 53.1 in Turland et al. (2018) as they are later homonyms of *H. davaoensis* Kloppenb. [*Hoya*

New 1(2): 9. 2013] and *H. samarensis* Kloppenb. & Siar (Asklepios 113: 29. 2012), respectively. Therefore, new names are proposed herein for these taxa.

Nomenclature

Hoya panyupayanaensis Sanjeet Kumar & R.Kr. Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Eriostemma samarense* Kloppenb., Hoya New 2(4): 4. 2014. *Hoya samarensis* (Kloppenb.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, J. Biodivers. Conservation 9(2): 132. 2025, *nom. illeg., non* Kloppenb. & Siar, Asklepios 113: 29. 2012.

Distribution: Endemic to Philippines.

Etymology: Named after Panyupayana, the historical name of Philippines.

Hoya robertii Sanjeet Kumar & R.Kr. Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Eriostemma davaoensis* Kloppenb., Hoya New 2(3): 26. 2014. *Hoya davaoensis* (Kloppenb.) R.Kr.Singh & Sanjeet Kumar, J. Biodivers. Conservation 9(2): 132. 2025, *nom. illeg., non* Kloppenb., Hoya New 1(2): 9. 2013.

Distribution: Endemic to Philippines.

Etymology: Named after Robert Dale Kloppenburg, American Botanist.

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